

DICTIONARY OF NATIONAL BIOGRAPHY (INDIA)

Authority

<i>Title:</i>	<i>Dictionary of National Biography (India)</i>
<i>Editor:</i>	<i>Siba Pada Sen</i>
<i>Publisher:</i>	<i>Institute of Historical Studies</i>
<i>First Volume</i>	<i>1972</i>
<i>Fourth Volume</i>	<i>1974</i>
<i>Place of Publication:</i>	<i>Calcutta, (Now Kolkata)</i>
<i>Contributors:</i>	<i>350 (250 are professional historians from major universities of India)</i>

Introduction

The present Dictionary of National Biography in four volumes is the first attempt of its kind in India, on the line of similar works in other countries. There are no doubt a few biographical collections available both in English and in Indian languages, but there are very limited in scope. The Dictionary of National Biography in India, of a kind similar to dictionaries in other countries.

The period covered by the National Biography is from 1800 to 1947. The period has been deliberately limited, to give it a distinctive character, which it has in Indian history. New ideas and new forces appeared in the early part of 19th century. In the supplementary project, covering the period 1947 to 1972 includes only those who belonged to the Indian union.

The Dictionary of National Biography project has taken nine years. The first year comprised of planning, setting up the necessary organizational machinery as well as appointing and training research fellows in different states. The next five year were taken up by collecting biographical material on the basis of an elaborate standard format. It was done by 32 research fellows in different states and regions working under the supervision of the local university professors. The next two years were taken up by the writing of actual biographical entries on

the basis of the material collected by the research fellows. The task was entrusted to nearly 350 contributors all over the country. In many cases they undertook additional labor to collect supplementary material and to checkup the material supplied by the research fellows of the contributors nearly or professional historian drawn from all the major universities in the country. The 9th year was fully taken up by editing work which had actually begun even earlier, in 1970.

Scope

- It is national in scope.
- It is comprehensive in nature.
- The purpose of Dictionary of National Biography is to know about the sacrifice of eminent persons for the present generation.
- The Dictionary of National Biography includes people from all spheres of life politics, religious and social reforms, education, journalism, literature, science, law, business and industry, etc- who had made strong tangible contribution to national life from the beginning to the 19th century to the achievements of independence.
- In the dictionary of national biography some categories of persons like musician, dancers, actors, sportsman, have been virtually left out of the purview of the present four volumes project, unless any of them happened to have made some positive contribution to the growth of national consciousness or to the development of society.
- DNB includes many people belonging to the area which later come to be known as Pakistan and Bangladesh, and also those who migrated from India to Pakistan the time of the partition or after. Because there was no Pakistan or Bangladesh before 1947
- Each volume contains approximately 300 to 350 biographical sketches. The total number of biographical entries included in the 4 volumes of the Dictionary of National Biography is nearly 1400.
- The intended of this DNB to fulfil that need and to give India the same type of biographical reference work, covering 19th and 20th centuries.
- It include person who may be still living at the time of publication, if they are deserving of inclusion in the dictionary
- Indian Language Source Material e.g., Biographies, General Works, newspapers, literary works, pamphlets etc. are used for gathering information.

Treatment

- The name of the leader is written in capital letters, followed by years of birth and death within bracket.
- The entry is divided into the following sections: personal and family details, early life, career, history, personality.
- At the end of each entry the name of the contributors is given in capital and small letters on the right side of the column.
- In some cases where this is not possible or where it would lead to confusion, the full name has been given, e.g. Bhagat Singh.
- In the dictionary of national biography volumes the names have been put in strict alphabetical order, irrespective of state or region, community, religion and caste
- In some cases the surname in an Indian language is spell differently in English, e.g. Datta, Dutta. So in the case for the convenience of the reader the different spelling of the surname have arranged them in a more rational manner as given below: - Datta, Dutt or Dutta have all put under Datta.
- A selected bibliography is given at the end of each entry.

Arrangement

- Biographical entries are arranged in alphabetical order according to the surname of the prominent person
- Cross Reference is given
- DNB arranged in four volumes.

Volume 1 A-D

Volume 2 E-L

Volume 3 M-R

Volume 4 S-Z

Format

- Dictionary of National Biography is available only in print format.
- The feature of dictionary of National Biography in print format is:
 - ✓ Two columns per page.
 - ✓ Volume sizes are similar.
 - ✓ Italics and Roman Font have been used for entries.
 - ✓ Fine paper quality is used.
 - ✓ Heading are in bold letters and text is in light ink.
 - ✓ It is in hard cover binding.
 - ✓ Clear and legible printings.

Special Features

- Practical hints for the reader are given with illustrative examples so they not face problem while consulting 'Dictionary of National Biography'.
- A selected bibliography is given at the end of each entry within brackets for serious readers.
- There is no bias on the basis of state or religion.

Drawbacks

- Dictionary of National Biography is not available online for readers.
- Notable sports figures have been omitted.
- No reference material on the post independence period is provided.
- In the biographical entries no rigid uniformity has been observed either in spelling of proper name or in use of punctuation marks.

- In some cases the surname in an Indian language is spelt differently in English which create confusion for a reader to find out the entry.
- The DNB in four volumes published in 1972-74 is out of print and now, outdated too. (According to Dictionary of Indian Biography).

Conclusion

As a whole, it concludes that Dictionary of National Biography will serve as a concrete illustration book for works on movements and forces in modern Indian History till 1947. It will help serious students to understand better some trends in modern Indian history and to assess the importance of different factors which went to the making of the modern history.

In sum up the DNB is a valuable reference work, a place to garner information regarding important person, and a starting point for further research. DNB aims to emphasize to new generation the invaluable contributions of early pioneers.

REFERENCE

Sen, S.P. (Ed.). (1947). *Dictionary of National Biography*, Vol.4, Institute of Historical Studies: Calcutta.